

Behavioral Change Pattern of Youths through Cyberbullying in Social Media: A Study among University Students in Rangpur

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ABSTRACT

The term cyberbullying, for its devastating consequences, has become a significant topic in recent years. Technological advances have constructed a fertile environment for cyberbullying, which is increasing rapidly. Social media platforms, such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, or YouTube, offer ground for generating and distributing cyberbullying content. This study aimed to investigate the behavioral change pattern through cyberbullying in social media. A quantitative survey method was used in the study. A simple random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample. The sample size was 393 (male 223, female 170). The study found that Facebook is the most cyberbullying-friendly media (94.15%). Almost half of the respondents have experienced cyberbullying, and 74.5% of respondents avoid it if they are bullied. Most respondents stated that cyberbullying changed their social, mental, economic, and physical behavior. Users who practice cyberbullying use different methods. These include posting cyberbullying content, mentioning, forwarding, sharing, reacting, and participating in cyberbullying discussions.

Keywords: social media, cyberbullying, behavioral change, youth, public university students.

INTRODUCTION

We live in the era of modern information and communication technologies (ICTs). There are hardly any people who can live without the internet, a tremendous blessing of ICTs. Our life is made more accessible than ever before by its greatest contributions. Despite blessings, it is a fact that the invention of the internet and modern communication technologies make the youths' lives more vulnerable than ever before because of cyberbullying. Bullying is not just fun; it is harmful to others. It is an addiction in which people get involved consciously or unconsciously. Telenor found that 85% of Bangladeshi youth say online bullying is a serious problem (85% of Youth in BD Says Online Bullying, 2021). Seeking to harm, intimidating, or coercing others is generally known as bullying. Bullying has no typical definition. This can happen in different types and ages.

Gathering information, exchanging information, entertaining, communicating with networks, shopping for daily life, and even creating our leisure time effectively, we use various mediums of the internet, i.e., social media. In this context, various types of crimes happen in the virtual realm; among them, cyberbullying is an important one. This is a new topic to discuss seriously in this social media age. Cyberbullying is a kind of harassment that is a barrier to the development of physical and mental health, such as calling someone by odd nicknames, derogatory name-calling, mocking, etc. Generally, introverts, bashful, funky, and self-centred people confess to more bullying on social media. Adolescent girls are just as likely, or even more likely, to be victims of cyberbullying than boys (both victims and perpetrators) (Cyberbullying Research Center, 2015).

Racial discrimination, gender discrimination, physical or bullying for sexual harassment, sadness, anger, frustration, humiliation, etc. The victims could also struggle academically because they might feel too ashamed to attend class or participate. Sometimes, the sufferers may even consider committing suicide. These are various effects of cyberbullying in social media (Social Media Victims Law Center, 2023). Our childhood is the basement of socialization, but approximately 20 percent of participants said they are being bullied at school (Psychology Today, 2019). The development of information and communication technology opened the window for cyberbullying. The prime factor of cyberbullying is the rise of the internet and social media. Day by day, it greatly affects our young generation (Kaur & Saini, 2023). Anger, low self-esteem, suicidal ideation, frustration, and other aspects of emotional and psychological problems result from cyberbullying (Brighi et al., 2012; Hinduja & Patchin, 2010; Hinduja & Patchin, 2019). So, we can easily say that our high online dependency is the root cause of fostering destructive or harmful behavior. Cyberbullying, a heinous instance of harmful or destructive behaviors, leads to serious societal problems.

Cyberbullying and online harassment are indicative problems for the users of social media websites, especially youth communities, as has been shown by recent research studies. Pachin and Hinduja (2006) defined cyberbullying as intentionally deliberate and continuous harassment using modern technology. Accidentally, internet use for cyberbullying might depict a strong argument for the heinous effects of online technology. For both individuals and organizations, the experience of cyberbullying has been associated with significant negative results such as anxiety, substance abuse, depression, eating disorders, sleep, and a decrease in academic performance (Beran & Li, 2005; Privitera & Campbell, 2009; Ybarra et al., 2007). That is why it is high time to be aware of cyberbullying.

Bangladesh has more than 44 million social media users (Report, 2023); a significant portion lives in the Rangpur region. As cyberbullying is a new term in cyberspace, it is a fact that most of the students have limited knowledge about this issue. The youths in the Rangpur region mostly suffer from different forms of bullying in silence due to social, physical, emotional, economic, and cultural constraints. In this study, the researcher tried to know how youth communities identify cyberbullying content in social media, what attitudes they show against cyberbullying, how they practice cyberbullying, etc., in association with the behavioral change pattern of youths due to cyberbullying. This study would be significant for academicians, students, professionals, companies, governments, non-government organizations and international development organizations. It would be helpful for academicians, students and professionals to conduct cyberbullying-related research in different parts of the country and present the scenarios against this trendy issue, which is deemed a heinous crime nationally and globally. Service providers might get an overview of how people use social media platforms to commit crimes in the virtual realm and the consequences of these crimes. They can take action against cyberbullying content as well as those who commit this heinous crime, according to the research findings.

In addition, the government might use this research finding as evidence to create and implement proper rules and regulations to make the virtual realm safe to eradicate this dreadful crime from Bangladesh. Again, the government may add cyberbullying as a textbook topic to make young students aware of it and educate them about it. We can also learn how cyberbullying affects youth's socio-economic, emotional and physical conditions

and what are the best practices against cyberbullying as well as it can present the devastating consequences of this act.

Furthermore, national and international nongovernment development organizations might plan campaign programs against cyberbullying. So, people may know how to identify cyberbullying content, understand the devastating results of it, take action against this serious crime and be aware of their child, friends and family members about cyberbullying so that they can fight against it.

Although there have been many studies on cyberbullying at national and international levels, such studies have yet to be conducted in the Rangpur region. This research gap and the significance of this research were the researchers' motivations behind the research. There has been a lot of research on cyberbullying globally. However, research has yet to be done on this pattern to the authors' knowledge. From that point of view, our research has originality and novelty. However, some variables of the study were taken from previous studies.

With the ongoing rise and growth in technology and social media, students of the Rangpur region should know how to identify and evaluate bullying in the virtual realm. The overall objective of this study is to know the behavioral change patterns of youths through cyberbullying in social media.

In this research, researchers investigate the following questions:

RQ1: What are the respondents' social media use trends?

RQ2: What is the knowledge about cyberbullying among respondents?

RQ3: What are the attitudes of respondents towards cyberbullying?

RQ4: What are the types of practices for cyberbullying among students?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The spread of social media platforms in today's digital world has significantly impacted young people's behavior patterns. But there is a darker side to this virtual connectedness, which takes the form of cyberbullying, a widespread problem that has effects that go beyond mental stress. An analysis of previous research is essential to contextualize and comprehend the subtleties of this intricate phenomenon, as this study looks at the behavioral shift patterns among university students in Rangpur as a result of cyberbullying. The purpose of this literature review is to present an overview of existing research on social media and its use, cyberbullying using social media, and behavior change due to cyberbullying.

SOCIAL MEDIA AND IT'S USING TREND

A collection of Web-based tools known as "social media" are founded on websites' ideologies and technological principles and facilitate the production and sharing of user-generated content. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Jean Burgess, an editor of the 'SAGE Handbook of Social Media' set a definition that by social media technologies, we mean those digital platforms, services, and apps built around the convergence of content sharing, public communication, and interpersonal connection (Burgess et al., 2017).

According to Hossain et al. (2020), around 94.44% of the population had social media accounts. The most attractive social media platform was Facebook (90.48%). Most of the respondents (80.95%) used social media for entertainment. Approximately 62.7% of the students spent time from 1 to 4 hours a day on social media usage. The use time gradually increased among 77.78% of respondents while they launched using social media. Another study was conducted by Johnston et al. (2013). They show that their respondents use Facebook to contact others for class work, group work and discussion. Akakandelwa and

Walubita (2018) conducted a study that revealed 70.9 percent of participants either regularly or occasionally spend more time on social media, and 75.8 percent often or occasionally check social media sites before doing anything else. Additionally, 60.8% of participants reported negative comments about their use of social media, and 55.9% reported feeling stressed out as a result of their use of social media. 42 percent respondents took into account themselves to be negatively affected by social media; 32 percent said that social media as often negatively affected; 21 percent ranked themselves as sometimes negatively affected by social media, and only 5 percent thought themselves as never negatively affected by the use of social media in their social life.

CYBERBULLYING: KNOWLEDGE, AFFECTED, PRACTICE MEDIA, AND BEHAVIOR CHANGE

Cyberbullying is a new issue of discussion in cyberspace. It was first created by Bill Belsi in 1999. People are victimized by cyberbullying in various ways like online abuse, websites, chat rooms, instant messaging, online messaging, blogs, cell phone text messages and so on (McLean, 2007). Cyberbullying is considered as an umbrella term to explore various kinds of online misuse such as harassment, doxing, defamation and revenge porn. To accomplish cyberbullying – the convict uses technology, including computers, consoles, cell phones and/or any other device. With access to the internet or social media platforms, the convict can harass, stalk or abuse other people by fermenting or participating in online hate campaigns. Cyberbullying is sending text online as well as delivering sexually explicit graphics or photos, and it aims to insult or contempt (Schrock & Boyd, 2008). It has become very common to engaging pornography distribution and harassment, threatening behavior as well as social exclusion (Hinduja and Pachin, 2009).

In 2010, Beebe researched cyberbullying, including 202 college students in the United States. Of the undergraduate students, about 50.7% reported having been victims of cyberbullying once or twice while attending college. Furthermore, around 36.3% of respondents suffered from cyberbullying victimization every month while in college. According to Dilmaç (2009), about 22.5% of 666 students at Selcuk University in Turkey suffered from a victim of cyberbullying another person at least once, and 55.35% reported being a victim of cyberbullying at least once in their lifetimes. 11% of the 131 students (from seven undergraduate courses in the United States) who participated in another study conducted by Carol et al. (2011) reported having encountered cyberbullying at their university. The survey also revealed that Facebook (64%), instant messaging (43%), and cell phones (43%) were the most often utilized technologies. According to student reports, 57% of cyberbullies were people from outside the institution, 50% happened through peers, and 43% of victims were unaware of the identity of the cyberbully. Pachin and Hinduja (2006) surveyed 384 people. They found that 11 per cent of the participants were involved with cyberbullying, 29 per cent were victimized by cyberbullying, and 50 per cent witnessed cyberbullying.

The use of technology is increasing worldwide in this modern era. Cyberspace has become popular with the invention of the Internet. The advent of social media makes cyberspace more popular. People have become more connected as the internet and modern technology give easy access to information and massive connectivity. There is grounding evidence of uniquely linked long-term negative outcomes of cyberbullying (Vaillancourt et al., 2017). Cyberbullying demonstrates psychological problems such as depression, anxiety, loneliness, low self-esteem, social exclusion, school phobias and poor academic performance (DeHue et al., 2008; Juvonen and Gross, 2008; Kowalski and Limber, 2007; Grene, 2003; Juvonen et al., 2003; Rivituso, 2012; Varghese and Pistole, 2017; Na, 2014; Akcil, 2018), low self-esteem, family problems, school violence and delinquent behaviour (Webber and Ovedovitz, 2018), which bounds to think them to suicidal experience as a means of removing the torture (Ghadampour et al., 2017).

Furthermore, studies by Carol et al. (2011) and Faryadi (2011) reveal the psychological and physical harm that cyberbullying causes to helpless victims, as well as the psychosocial issues that include improper behavior, alcohol consumption, smoking, and despair. Additionally, Faryadi (2011) discovered that victims of cyberbullying experience severe mental distress and

find it difficult to focus on their academics, and as a result, their academic performance suffers greatly. Most of the participants (85%) believed that cyberbullying had an impact on their academic performance, particularly on their grades.

METHODOLOGY

Researchers employed a quantitative survey method to acquire the goals of this research. Begum Rokaya University, Rangpur (BRUR) and Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science & Technology University (HSTU), Dinajpur, are two universities of the greater Rangpur region that were selected purposively as the study area. As researchers found no research on the issue in this study area, they chose the area, although this sampling procedure has some drawbacks. However, participants in the study were selected through simple random sampling, where every respondent had the same opportunity to be the sample. Before collecting the data, informed consent was taken from the respondents. They were also ensured that their response would not be used for other purposes besides research. Participation was voluntary. Researchers provided 400 printed questionnaires to various discipline students and told them to read carefully and answer all the closed-ended questions. Among them, seven participants' responses were incomplete. By excluding the incomplete responses, researchers used 393 respondents' responses for the final analysis. Before conducting the final survey, a pretest was performed among 30 students. In developing the research questionnaire, the researcher mainly follows the KAP Survey theory, although it was developed to measure changes in health behavior. It is urgent to know the respondents' knowledge level about cyberbullying in social media. Here, the researchers tried their best to discover youths' behavioral change patterns due to cyberbullying and the practices the respondents did. The questionnaire was divided into five (5) portions; the first portion was respondents' demographic data such as gender, age, educational qualification, marital status, etc., i.e., five (5) questions were used. In the second part, the researcher includes four (4) questions regarding respondents' social media use trends. The third section was the knowledge level of cyberbullying, where thirteen (13) questions were used to measure the respondents' knowledge. After that, in the fourth part, the researcher used twenty-four (24) behavioral feature statements to determine the behavior change due to cyberbullying, segmented into four categories: social, mental, economic, and physical change. The next (fifth) section adopted six questions measuring the practices of cyberbullying in social media.

DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data were coded and decoded according to the research objectives. Frequency distribution was calculated using the MS Excel system to analyze the items relating to demographic characteristics, knowledge, attitudes, and practices about cyberbullying. The Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) v.23.0 was used to analyze social media using trends where descriptive statistics (e.g., Mean, Standard deviation, minimum and maximum values) were used.

RESULTS

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Table 1. Demographic information of the respondents

Variable	Dimension	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Institutions	BRUR	290	26.21
	HSTU	103	73.79
	Total	393	100
Age	19-21 Years	132	33.58
	22-24 Years	208	52.93
	25-27 Years	53	13.49
	Total	393	100
Gender	Male	223	56.74
	Female	167	43.26
	Total	393	100
Marital Status	Married	24	6.11
	Unmarried	369	93.89
	Total	393	100
Year of the studies	1 st year	52	13.23
	2 nd year	146	37.15
	3 rd year	65	16.54
	4 th year	64	16.28
	MS/MBA/MSC	66	16.80
	Total	393	100

Data was collected from two universities in Bangladesh to examine the change in university students' behavior. Three hundred ninety-three (393) students participated in this study. Most students responded from BRUR 290 (73.79%) and the rest from HSTU 103 (26.21%). The finding shows that the participants' age was between 19 to 27 years (table 1). The majority of 208 (52.93%) respondents were 22 to 24 years old, and 132 (33.58%) were 19 to 21. The following 53 (13.49%) were 25 to 27 years old. Most of the participants were male, who was 223 (56.74%) of the participants. The rest (167(43.26%)) were female. Findings show that almost all 369 (93.89%) of the participants were unmarried, and only 24 (6.11%) of the respondents were married. The result depicts the respondents' study year. The result shows that 52 (13.23%) of the respondents were in their first year, 146 (37.15%) of the respondents were in their second year, 65 (16.54%) of the respondents were in their third year, and 64 (16.28%) of the respondents were the fourth year and 66(16.80%) of the respondents were masters' students (table 1).

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF SOCIAL MEDIA USING TRENDS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of social media using trends of the respondents

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Types of devices	393	1	3	1.61	0.92
Number of social media used	393	1	5	3.89	1.37
Daily frequency of visiting social media	393	1	10	5.97	2.82
Daily time spent on social media	393	1	15	4.55	2.25

The researcher presented the respondents' social media using trends in Table 2. Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and minimum and maximum values of descriptive statistics were used to present the social media using trend information. The finding revealed that the device used for accessing social media (M=1.61, SD=0.92), the number of social media users (M=3.89, SD=1.37) where the minimum used social media platform was one. The maximum was 5, the daily frequency of visiting social media (M=5.97, SD=2.82), and daily time spent on social media (M=4.55, SD=2.25). The minimum and maximum scores of the time spent were 1 and 15, respectively (table 2).

KNOWLEDGE ABOUT CYBERBULLYING

Table 3. Knowledge about cyberbullying

Variable	Dimension	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sending offensive messages repeatedly (online harassment)	Yes	348	88.55
	No	45	11.45
Sending rude or bitter messages about a person (flaming)	Yes	341	88.77
	No	52	11.23
Threatening with offensive messages (cyberstalking)	Yes	338	86.00
	No	55	14.0
Sending false or misleading information about a person (denigration)	Yes	320	81.42
	No	73	18.58
Sending messages camouflaged as someone else (impersonation)	Yes	304	77.35
	No	89	22.65
Sharing confidential information obtained through personal relationships with others (trickery)	Yes	288	73.28
	No	105	26.72
Consciously avoiding someone, like someone is doing something (exclusion)	Yes	189	48.09
	No	204	51.91
Sending sensitive messages like nude pictures	Yes	346	88.04
	No	47	11.96

There are various forms of cyberbullying, such as online harassment, flaming, cyberstalking, denigration, impersonation, trickery, and exclusion. Table 3 represents the different statements related to cyberbullying forms and styles. Researchers used these to measure the respondent's knowledge about cyberbullying. Each variable consists of 100 values every time. Here, firstly, sending offensive messages repeatedly (online harassment), 348 (88.55%) respondents said affirmative (said yes), and 45 (11.45%) respondents said negatively (said no). Secondly, regarding the question of sending rude or bitter messages about a person (flaming), 341 (88.77%) respondents said yes, and 52(11.23%) said no. Thirdly, the researcher asked respondents whether someone threatened them with offensive messages (cyberstalking). 338 (86%) respondents said yes, and 55(14%) said no. Sending false or misleading information about a person (denigration) here 320 (81.42%) respondents said affirmative, but 73 (18.58%) respondents said their answer negatively. Sending messages camouflaged as someone else (impersonation), 304 (77.35%) respondents answered yes, and 89(22.65%) were no. Sharing confidential information obtained through personal relationships with others (trickery), 288 (73.28%) respondents said yes, and 105(26.72%) said no. Consciously avoiding someone, like someone is doing something (exclusion), 189(48.09%) respondents said their answer positively, but 204(51.91%) were given their answer negatively. Sending sensitive messages like nude pictures, 346 (88.04%) respondents said yes, but 47 (11.96%) respondents said no (table 3).

ATTITUDES ABOUT CYBERBULLYING

BEHAVIORAL CHANGE OF THE RESPONDENTS DUE TO CYBERBULLYING

Table 4. Participants' behavioral change due to cyberbullying

Types of Changing Behaviours	Variable	Dimension	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Social behavioural change	Changing social condition	Yes	315	80.15
		No	78	19.85
	Moving away from social media	Yes	233	59.29
		No	160	40.71
	Avoiding pair groups	Yes	271	68.96
		No	122	31.04
	Decreasing self-esteem	Yes	298	75.83
		No	95	24.17
	Decreasing social activity participation	Yes	323	59.00
		No	70	41.00
Disrupting study	Yes	343	87.27	
	No	50	12.73	
Mental behavioural change	Changing mental condition	Yes	353	89.82
		No	40	10.18
	Giving birth to frustration	Yes	352	89.57
		No	41	10.43
	Suffering from loneliness	Yes	334	80.99
		No	59	10.01
	Increasing mental instability	Yes	352	89.57
		No	41	10.43
	Creating negative perceptions toward society	Yes	334	80.99
		No	59	10.01
Decreasing ability to deal with a situation	Yes	234	59.54	
	No	159	40.46	
Economic behavioural change	Changing economic condition	Yes	208	52.92
		No	185	47.08
	Creating aversion to work	Yes	316	80.40
		No	77	19.60
	Cannot concentrate on work	Yes	335	85.24
		No	58	14.76
	Continuous absence in the workplace	Yes	299	76.08
		No	94	23.92
	Income capacity decrease	Yes	261	66.41
		No	132	33.59
Quitting job	Yes	225	57.25	
	No	168	42.75	
	Changing physical condition	Yes	263	66.92
		No	130	33.08
	Happening sleeping disturbance	Yes	341	86.77
		No	52	13.23
		Yes	312	79.39

Physical behavioural change	Creating aversion to food	No	81	20.61
		Yes	325	82.70
	Increasing health risk	No	68	17.30
		Yes	332	84.48
	Decreasing ability to work	No	61	15.52
		Yes	308	78.37
	Choosing suicide paths	No	85	21.63
		Yes	316	79.37

Table 4 shows that Social, Mental, Economic, and Physical behavioral changes are closely connected to cyberbullying. We used six variables that indicate social behavioral change due to cyberbullying. Every variable consists of 100 values for each time. Firstly, regarding changing social conditions, 315 (80.15%) respondents said affirmative (said yes), and 78 (19.85%) respondents said negative (said no). Secondly, moving away from social media, 233(59.29%) participants said yes, and 160(40.71%) said no. Thirdly, the researcher asked respondents questions on avoiding pair groups, where 271(68.96%) respondents said yes, and 122(31.04%) said no. Decreasing self-esteem due to cyberbullying here 298(75.83%) respondents were affirmative, but 95 (24.17%) respondents said their answer was negative. Decreasing social activities participation, 323(59.0%) respondents answered positively and 70(41.00%) were no. Disrupting the study due to cyberbullying, 343 (87.27%) respondents said yes, and 50(12.73%) were no.

For measuring mental behavior change due to cyberbullying, we use six variables. Every variable consists of 100 values for each time. The majority (353) of the respondents said their mental condition changed due to cyberbullying, whereas 40 gave negative opinions. The statement cyberbullying gives birth to frustration, where 352 agreed that 41 were not. Most of the 334 respondents said cyberbullying causes suffering from loneliness; on the other hand, 59 said no. Increasing mental instability got 334 positive answers, where 41 answered negatively. Cyberbullying causes negative perceptions towards society, resulting in increasing mental instability. Another result of cyberbullying is the decreasing ability to deal with situations, with 234 positive responses and 159 saying it does not happen (table 4).

The results also show the economic behavioral change due to cyberbullying. Here are six variables used for measuring. Every variable consists of 100 values for each time. More than half (208) of the respondents said their economic conditions changed due to cyberbullying, whereas 185 gave negative opinions. Cyberbullying creates an aversion to work, where 316 agreed, but 77 disagreed. Most (335) respondents said cyberbullying results in concentration breaks at work; on the other side, 58 said no. Continuing absence in the workplace got 299 positive answers, where 94 answered negatively. Cyberbullying results in declining income and received 261 responses positively, where 132 were negative responses. Another result of cyberbullying is quitting a job, which got 225 positive responses, where 168 said it does not happen.

Table 4 depicts the physical behavioral change due to cyberbullying. Six variables were used to identify physical behavioral change. Every variable consists of 100 values for each time. Firstly, regarding changing physical condition due to cyberbullying, 263 (66.92%) respondents said affirmative (said yes), and 130 (33.08%) responders said negative (said no). Secondly, regarding the question of sleeping disturbance, 341 (86.77%) respondents said yes, and 52(13.23%) said no. Thirdly, the researcher has asked questions to respondents, creating an aversion to food due to cyberbullying. Here, 312 (79.39%) respondents said yes, and 81 (20.61%) were no. Increasing health risk, 325(82.70%) respondents said affirmative, but 68 (17.30%) responders said their answer negatively. Decreasing ability to work got 332(84.48%) positive responses, whereas 61(15.52%) were negative. Another serious result of cyberbullying is choosing suicide paths; here, 308 (78.37%) respondents believe this happens, and 85(21.33%) said that it does not happen (table 4).

PRACTICE ABOUT CYBERBULLYING

Table 5. Types of cyberbullying practice in social media

Types of Practice of Cyberbullying	Variable	Dimension	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Posting	Posting cyberbullying content on social media	Yes	35	8.91
		No	358	91.09
Mentioning	Mentioning a content	Yes	49	12.47
		No	344	87.53
Forwarding	Forwarding cyberbullying content	Yes	37	9.41
		No	356	90.59
Sharing	Sharing cyberbullying content with others	Yes	54	13.74
		No	339	86.26
Reacting	Reacting to cyberbullying content	Yes	158	40.20
		No	235	59.80
Participating discussion	Participating cyberbullying discussion	Yes	84	21.37
		No	309	78.63

Cyberbullying is increasing daily on online platforms, especially social media platforms. It takes place in these mediums using different methods. These patterns include posting cyberbullying content, mentioning and forwarding, sharing, reacting, and participating in cyberbullying discussions. Table 5 depicts that only 35 (8.91%) respondents post cyberbullying content on social media. On the contrary, a huge number of participants in the study, 358 (91.09%), do not post cyberbullying content on social media. The study also found that a few of them (12.47%) do mention someone in cyberbullying content. Conversely, many people (87.53%) never mention someone in cyberbullying content. The following table shows that 37 (9.41%) forward cyberbullying content on social media. However, on the other side, 356 (90.59%) people never forward cyberbullying content on social media. A few students (13.74%) shared cyberbullying content on social media, but a huge number of participants in the study, 339 (86.26%), said they do not share cyberbullying content on social media. The table shows that 158 (40.20%) reacted to cyberbullying content; on the other hand, 235 (59.80%) people never responded to cyberbullying content. The following table revealed that 21.37% (84) of respondents participated in a cyberbullying discussion; on the contrary, most participants, 78.63% (309), did not participate in a cyberbullying discussion (table 5).

DISCUSSION

To investigate the behavioural change pattern of youths through cyberbullying in social media, the researcher collects and analyses the data from two universities in the Rangpur region. The behaviour change of youths highly depends on the respondents' knowledge about cyberbullying, attitudes towards cyberbullying, and the practices they do in social media in association with cyberbullying. These variables also depend on the respondents' demographic characteristics and social media trends. Respondents are from two universities in Bangladesh, both male and female, undergraduate and postgraduate students aged between 19 and 27. All the youths in this study use social media. Previous research in this region shows similar results (Hossain et al., 2020; Prodhan et al., 2020). The results for spending time on social media daily

were 1 to 5 hours for 75.6% of respondents. A similar study by Hossain and Prodhan (2020) stated that about 63.06% of the respondents spent 1 to 4 hours daily on social media.

The finding shows that respondents have enough knowledge about cyberbullying. To investigate the knowledge about different forms of cyberbullying, researchers provided eight (8) statements about whether they know. Nearly 80 percent of the participants said they knew about these.

To know the respondents' attitudes towards cyberbullying, the researcher provides some statements about social changes due to cyberbullying. More than half of the participants gave affirmative answers about these statements. Various similar studies proved these social changes, such as avoiding friends or social events and home isolation, more than conventional. The victims become quieter or dispelled from their surroundings. It is found that it is hard to concentrate on schoolwork, grades drop, and interest in activities is lost (Kaspersky, 2022). 85% of respondents believe cyberbullying affected their academic performance (Faryadi, 2011).

Regarding mental change, respondents mentioned that their mental condition changed due to cyberbullying. They also said that cyberbullying gives birth to frustration, causes suffering from loneliness, increasing mental instability, negative perceptions towards society, increasing mental instability, and decreased ability to deal with the situation. Carol et al. (2011) researched that cyberbullying pursues emotional and physiological harm to defenceless oblation (Faryadi, 2011) as well as psychosocial problems such as awkward behaviours, alcohol consumption, depression, and smoking. Some other studies revealed that cyberbullying demonstrates psychological issues such as depression, anxiety, loneliness, low self-esteem, social exclusion, school phobias, and poor academic performance (DeHue et al., 2008; Juvonen & Gross, 2008; Kowalski & Limber, 2007; Grene, 2003; Juvonen et al., 2003; Rivituso, 2012; Varghese & Pistole, 2017; Na, 2014; Akcil, 2018), low self-esteem, family problems, school violence, and delinquent behaviour (Webber & Ovedovitz, 2018).

More than half (208) of the respondents said their economic condition was changed due to cyberbullying. In the case of psychical behavioural change, we found that cyberbullying changes participants' physical condition, sleeping disturbance, aversion to food, increasing health risk, and decreasing ability to work, and it leads them to choose suicide paths. A previous study conducted by Ghadampour et al. (2017) mentions that their respondents said that cyberbullying causes them to think of suicidal experiences as a means of removing the torture.

The present study depicts the social media features used in committing cyberbullying to assess if they cyberbully, where only 8.91% of people post cyberbullying content on social media, and 91.09% do not post. 12.47% do mention someone in cyberbullying content, and 87.53% do never mention someone. 9.41% of people forward cyberbullying content, and 90.59% never forward cyberbullying content on social media. The study also found that 13.74% share cyberbullying content, 86.26% do not share, 40.20% react to cyberbullying content, and 59.80% give no reaction. In addition, 21.37% of respondents participated in a cyberbullying discussion, and 78.63% of 309 did not participate in a cyberbullying discussion.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Researchers faced many problems in conducting this research but tried their best to overcome all the complexities. That is why some limitations have existed in this study. These were-

The first limitation of this study was the sample size. Only 393 students were sampled, an insignificant number considering the population of the two public universities. So, it is impossible to generalize the study findings for all the university students of Bangladesh and the globe. The second, only questionnaire-based survey method was used. Here, the researcher used only

this technique to identify the behavioral change pattern of youths through cyberbullying in social media.

FUTURE DIRECTION

Only a quantitative survey method was applied to investigate the behavioral change through cyberbullying. So, in future studies, the researchers need to apply field observation, focus group discussions, In-depth interviews, recordings made in natural settings, etc. Another recommendation is to select a sample that can be generalized nationwide and represents the global scenarios of behavioral change patterns through cyberbullying.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to determine the behavioral change pattern through cyberbullying. After analyzing the study findings, the study outlines that the behavioral change pattern depends on the respondents' knowledge, their attitudes towards cyberbullying, and the practices they do on social media sites. When a student has enough knowledge about cyberbullying and the devastating consequences of cyberbullying on others, they may abstain from bullying others on social media. Their practice depends on their knowledge level and their attitudes towards cyberbullying. The study concluded that social media features like posts, comments, mentions, etc., can be used for committing cyberbullying incidents in social media.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study. Informed consent was obtained from every participant in this study, and all procedures were carried out in compliance with the ethical requirements of the institutional research guidelines.

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